

Accessible Zoom with a Screen Reader

This workshop will be offered in Spanish. [Dates and registration form \(in Spanish\)](#)

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Objectives

In this workshop we will be learning how to use Zoom with the NVDA screen reader. We recommend to [watch this 5 minute video](#) that explains how to download and install the screen reader.

Download and install NVDA [👉 https://nvda.es/descargas/descarga-de-nvda/](https://nvda.es/descargas/descarga-de-nvda/)

At the end of this workshop, those who complete it will be able to:

- Modify Zoom shortcut settings.
- Use the Zoom and NVDA tools simultaneously.
- Use the full functionality of the Zoom tool during a synchronous meeting.

Intended public of this course

This workshop is oriented to people with visual impairment and teachers of persons with visual impairment.

Attendees should know how to join a Zoom meeting and install the NVDA screen reader Video walkthrough for downloading and installing NVDA prior to the workshop: <https://youtu.be/jaOp891hAnY>

Check out [personas](#) to read more about them.

How to participate

This workshop will be offered in Spanish. [Dates and registration form \(in Spanish\)](#).

The workshop is free. Those invited to the workshop agree to abide by our [code of conduct](#).

Duration

This is a 2-hour workshop with 5 to 10 minutes break every 50 minutes.

Schedule

We will start by showing the Zoom tool shortcuts before launching a meeting. We will continue showing the shortcuts within a meeting from the most used to the most general. We will detail the functionality of each shortcut allowing live training.

Course materials (in Spanish)

[Course materials \(in Spanish\)](#)

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